

Practice Abstract no. 30

Recipe recommendation systems

(Updated for 2025)

Poor nutrition is a critical modern health problem, strongly linked to non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, and cancer [1, 2].

As general and population-wide diets often fail due to individual characteristics and responses, personalised and precision nutrition (based on genetic and lifestyle factors) are essential, particularly for those with chronic conditions.

Advancing personalised nutrition increasingly relies on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML). These technologies power recommendation systems by recognising food and ingredients, and can also be used for disease detection [3]. To make these systems work, large individual health datasets must be collected, including metrics such as heart rate and body fat.

This Practice Abstract addresses Recipe Recommendation Systems, one of several recommenders in personalised nutrition. These systems can help individuals maintain healthier diets by suggesting tailored recipes and can also use personal data and image recognition to deliver accurate suggestions. A selection of the more recent researched features explored for recipe recommendation systems include:

- Development of a structured approach to extract and predict recipe information using advanced machine learning models such as Parallel-CNN, Naïve Bayes, Fuzzy logic, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). This method effectively caters to various user needs, including dietary preferences, allergies, and food intolerances. [4]
- Development of a Health-aware Food Recommendation System (FRS) with Dual Attention in Heterogeneous Graphs (DAHG). This system uses unsupervised learning on graph-structured data to recommend both healthy and popular recipes, surpassing existing methods in performance on the Allrecipes dataset. [5]
- Introduction of an Intelligent Nutrition Assistant Application (INAA), a web-based platform that uses AI and ML algorithms to offer personalised dietary recommendations. The platform was initially validated by 50 users, with plans to enhance the system further with more advanced ML techniques and a larger food database. [6]
- Development of the "Smart Cuisine," a system powered by AI technologies such as the Generative Pre-training Transformer (GPT) model, which provides personalised recipes and nutritional advice while promoting sustainable cooking practices. The system processes food images and uses natural language processing to generate customised recipes and nutritional insights. [7]

- Launch of the CookPal application, a website where users can either upload an image of one or more products or write down those products and the system's algorithm will produce a recipe with the identified/ listed products. [8]

Recipe recommendation systems represent a promising way to deliver personalised nutrition based on individual profiles and preferences. With data-driven technologies like image processing and graph models, these systems can help people achieve tailored and nutritionally sound diets.

References

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